

AWARENESS OF B.Ed. STUDENTS TOWARDS INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT)

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Abstract

Information and Communication Technology has involved any product that will store, retrieve, manipulate, transmit or receive information electronically in a digital form. This paper highlights the various awareness B.Ed. students towards ICT. The present study is undertaken to study the level of B.Ed. students towards the awareness of ICT. The major objective of the study is to find out the difference between (i) male and female and (ii) Government and Unaided Colleges B.Ed. students towards the awareness of ICT and to find out the difference among undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. Students. 236 samples were taken from B.Ed. students from ten colleges of education (B.Ed. College) in Thanjavur and Pudukottai Districts affiliated to Tamil Nadu Teacher Education University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu. The data were collected by self made questionnaire. Special attention was given to factors like gender, type of college and degree of B.Ed. Students. The data were analysed by using percentage analysis, 't' test and ANOVA. Results revealed that the level of awareness of ICT was moderate, there is no significant difference between (i) male and female and (ii) Government and Unaided colleges B.Ed. students towards ICT and there is no significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate, M.Phil. degree B.Ed. students towards ICT.

Key words: Information, Communication, Technology, ICT, Awareness

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology is the fusion of computers and telecommunications. It describes exiting and innovative ways to provide life long learners with global access to information, leaving and support. Computers enable people to work creatively. It can be used discussing, questioning, supporting a partner, debating, sharing data, analyzing, seeking, collecting, organizing, and on-line information and exploring real world. According to UNESCO (1998): Information and Communication Technology can be considered as the "Scientific, technological and engineering disciplines and the management techniques used in information handling and processing, their application. Computers and their interaction with men and machines and associated social, economical and cultural matters". Information and communications technology (ICT) is the hardware and software that enables data to be digitally process, store and communicated. ICT can be used to access, process, manage and present information; model and control

events; construct new understanding; and communicate with others.

Significance of the study

Awareness of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) refers to one's knowledge about educational radio like Gyan Vani, educational televisions like Gyan Darshan, internet, and computer based programme, CD-ROM, computer aided/assisted instruction, web-based learning, multi media, teleconferencing, video-conferencing, virtual reality, internal tutoring system, e-learning and e-content. Awareness of ICT is very important in helping B.Ed. students to learn and achieve good in their teaching pedagogical subjects. It knows to about the computer and internet components like how they work; how they help to solve problems while teaching. This can be learnt by seeing pictures, visiting internet through smart board, listening to talks or written reports and assignments. It makes an understanding of what an ICT are how it works and the role and impact of ICT in teaching-learning

process in the classroom. The investigator attempts to gain valuable insight into the awareness of B.Ed. students towards ICT.

The present study differs from the studies in terms of population, area and sample; hence the present investigation gains its relevance and significance.

Objectives

1. To find out the level of B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology (ICT).
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.
3. To find out the significant difference if any between Government and Unaided(self-finance)colleges B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.
4. To find out whether there is any significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. degree B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.
2. There is no significant difference between Government and Unaided (self-finance) colleges B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.
3. There is no significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. degree B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.

Methodology

The investigator has adopted the survey method of research to study the awareness of B.Ed. students towards information and communication technology (ICT).

Stratified random sampling techniques of 236 B.Ed. students were taken for this investigation. The above samples were taken from the B.Ed. students who are studying in ten colleges of education (B.Ed. Colleges) in Thanjavur and Pudukottai Districts affiliated to Tamil Nadu Teacher Education University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India, of whom 102 are male and 134 are female.

Special attention was given to factors like gender, type of college and degree of B.Ed. Students. Awareness of ICT Scale is developed and validated by the investigator was used to collect the data.

The data were analysed using percentage analysis, 't' test and ANOVA. The results of the study were presented in the following tables.

Analysis and inferences

The level of B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology (ICT) is as follows. It is inferred from the table that 0.4% of B.Ed. students have low, 94.1% of them have moderate and 5.5% of them have high level of awareness of radio.

It is understood from the table that 9.3% of B.Ed. students have low, 84.7% of them have moderate and 5.9% of them have high level of awareness of educational television.

It is clear from the table that 6.8% of B.Ed. students have low, 92.8% of them have moderate and 0.4% of them have high level of awareness of computer.

It is elegant from the table that 32.2% of B.Ed. students have low, 67.8% of them have moderate and zero percent of them have high level of awareness of CD ROM.

Table-1: Level of B.Ed. students' awareness towards ICT

Awareness of ICT	Low		Moderate		High	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Educational Radio Awareness	1	0.4	222	94.1	13	5.5
Educational Television Awareness	22	9.3	200	84.7	14	5.9
Computer Awareness	16	6.8	219	92.8	1	0.4
CD-ROM Awareness	76	32.2	160	67.8	0	0
Comp. Assisted Instr./Learning Awar.	199	84.3	36	15.3	1	0.4
Internet Awareness	34	14.4	202	85.6	0	0
Teleconferencing Awareness	40	16.9	171	72.5	25	10.6
Videoconferencing Awareness	32	13.6	148	62.7	56	23.7
E-Learning Awareness	36	15.3	121	51.3	79	33.5
ICT Awareness	5	2.1	130	55.1	101	42.8

It is found from the table that 84.3% of B.Ed. students have low, 15.3% of them have moderate and 0.4% of them have high level of awareness of Computer assisted/learning. It is elaborate from the table that 14.4% of B.Ed. students have low, 85.6% of them have moderate and zero percent of them have high level of awareness of internet. It is inferred from the table that 16.9% of B.Ed. students have low, 72.5% of them have moderate and 10.6% of them have high level of awareness of teleconferencing. The table reveals that 13.6% of B.Ed. students have low, 62.7% of them have moderate and 23.7% of them

have high level of awareness of videoconferencing. It is found from the table that 15.3% of B.Ed. students have low, 51.3% of them have moderate and 33.5% of them have high level of awareness of e-learning. It is clear from the table that 2.1% of B.Ed. students have low, 55.1% of them have moderate and 42.8% of them have high level of awareness of ICT.

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.

Table-2: difference between Male and Female B.Ed. students towards awareness of ICT

Variables	Male (n=102)		Female (n=134)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Radio Awareness	7.47	1.63	7.65	1.67	0.853	NS
Educational Television Awar.	10.98	2.45	10.85	2.65	0.384	NS
Computer Awareness	8.16	1.71	8.41	1.69	1.124	NS
CD-ROM Awareness	7.24	1.98	7.26	1.94	0.091	NS
Computer Assisted Instruction/ Learning Awareness	7.39	2.23	7.64	2.26	0.869	NS
Internet Awareness	7.44	2.10	8.00	2.10	2.046	S
Teleconferencing Awareness	7.18	1.71	7.39	1.71	0.930	NS
Videoconferencing Awareness	8.99	2.40	9.53	2.25	1.796	NS
E-Learning Awareness	7.47	1.68	7.61	1.86	0.634	NS
ICT Awareness	72.34	10.04	74.40	12.02	1.398	NS

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table that there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students towards the awareness of radio, educational television, computer, CD-ROM, computer assisted/learning, teleconferencing, videoconferencing and e-learning, as the calculated 't' values 0.853, 0.384, 1.124, 0.091, 0.869, 0.930, 1.796 and 0.634 are lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. But there is significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students towards the awareness of internet, as the calculated 't' value 2.046 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. While comparing the mean

scores, the female students are higher in their awareness of internet than the male B.Ed. students. In general, there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students towards the awareness of ICT, as the calculated 't' value 1.398 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between Government and Unaided (self-finance) colleges B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.

Table-3: Difference between Government and Unaided (Self-finance) colleges B.Ed. Students towards awareness of ICT

Variables	Government (n=56)		Unaided (n=180)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Radio Awareness	7.67	1.63	7.54	1.67	0.527	NS
Educational Television Awar.	10.75	2.57	10.95	2.56	0.523	NS
Computer Awareness	8.19	1.92	8.34	1.62	0.568	NS
CD-ROM Awareness	7.01	2.11	7.33	1.90	1.053	NS
Computer Assisted Instruction/ Learning Awareness	7.12	1.68	7.66	2.38	1.578	NS
Internet Awareness	7.41	1.89	7.87	2.17	1.425	NS
Teleconferencing Awareness	7.08	1.50	7.37	1.76	1.081	NS
Videoconferencing Awareness	8.82	2.16	9.48	2.36	1.771	NS
E-Learning Awareness	7.41	1.60	7.60	1.83	0.692	NS
ICT Awareness	71.50	10.17	74.13	11.50	1.539	NS

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table that there is no significant difference between Government and Unaided colleges B.Ed. students towards the awareness of radio, educational television, computer, CD-ROM, computer assisted/ learning, internet, teleconferencing, videoconferencing and e-learning, as the calculated 't' values 0.527, 0.523, 0.568, 1.053, 1.578, 1.425, 1.081, 1.771, and 0.692 are lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. In general there is no significant difference between Government

and Unaided colleges B.Ed. students towards the awareness of ICT, as the calculated 't' value 1.539 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.

Table-4: The ‘f’ value among Undergraduate, Postgraduate, and M.Phil. B.Ed. Students Towards Awareness of ICT

Variables	Sum of Variations	Sum of Squares	MSV	‘F’ Value	Remarks at 5% level
Radio Awareness	Between	4.583	2.291	0.830	NS
	Within	643.04	2.760		
Educational Television Awareness	Between	1.801	0.900	0.136	NS
	Within	1546.14	6.636		
Computer Awareness	Between	0.606	0.303	0.104	NS
	Within	679.81	2.918		
CD-ROM Awareness	Between	1.618	0.809	0.210	NS
	Within	899.65	3.861		
Computer Assisted Instruction/ Learning Awareness	Between	3.211	1.606	0.315	NS
	Within	1187.445	5.096		
Internet Awareness	Between	7.920	3.960	0.880	NS
	Within	1048.79	4.501		
Teleconferencing Awareness	Between	2.554	1.277	0.434	NS
	Within	685.479	2.942		
Videoconferencing Awareness	Between	9.484	4.742	0.873	NS
	Within	1266.156	5.434		
E-Learning Awareness	Between	4.675	2.337	0.732	NS
	Within	73.609	3.191		
ICT Awareness	Between	25.681	12.840	0.101	NS
	Within	29647.281	127.24		

(At 5% level of significance for 2, 233 df the table value of ‘F’ is 3.04)

From the above table it is understood that there is no significant difference among the undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. degree of B.Ed. students towards the awareness of the awareness of radio, educational television, computer, CD-ROM, computer assisted/learning, internet, teleconferencing, videoconferencing and e-learning, as the respective calculated ‘F’ values 0.830, 0.136, 0.104, 0.210, 0.315, 0.880, 0.434, 0.873 and 0.732 are lower than the table value 3.04 at 5% level of significance.

In general, there is no significant difference among the undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. degree of B.Ed. students towards the awareness of the awareness of ICT, as

the calculated ‘F’ value 0.101 is lower than the table value 3.04 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Findings

1. The 55.1 percent of B.Ed. students have moderate level of awareness on ICT.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.
3. There is no significant difference between Government and Unaided (self-finance) colleges B.Ed. students

towards the awareness of information and communication technology.

4. There is no significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. degree B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.

Discussions

Information and Communication Technology describes exiting and innovative ways to provide life long learning with global access to information, leaving and support. Likewise, the findings of the present study reveal that majority of the B.Ed. students employ their teaching pedagogical subjectsthrough the utilization of ICT components at moderate level. The 't' test results reveal that there is no significant difference between male and female B.Ed. students towards the awareness of ICT. The above finding of the present study is supported by the results of the investigation made by Philomina and Amutha (2016) that there no significant difference between the awareness of male and female teacher educators towards ICT. Khedekar and Magre (2012) found that there was no significant difference in awareness about Information and Communication Technology of Secondary students with respect to Gender. Similarly, there is no significant difference between Government and Unaided (self-finance) colleges B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology and there is no significant difference among undergraduate, postgraduate and M.Phil. degree B.Ed. students towards the awareness of information and communication technology.

Conclusion

The present study clearly indicated that the awareness of B.Ed. students towards ICT could benefit them with effective use of ICT tools. In this, awareness of B.Ed. students towards ICT, has more beneficiaries because ICT based teaching pedagogical subjects and core process may lead to effective, individual differences and efficacy in

teaching. Moreover, the B.Ed. students may mastery over the teaching learning through ICT. It may increase their ability to expose them in the classroom environment with the ICT components. It is expected that the B.Ed. students are fully aware of ICT and has bright future for teaching learning.

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